

The logo for EVOLVE2CARE features a large, light blue speech bubble shape. Below the bottom edge of the bubble is a stylized blue wave. Underneath the wave is a horizontal row of seven dark blue circles of varying sizes, arranged in a slightly curved pattern.

EVOLVE2CARE

D2.3 – Training Program for Living Labs

WP2 – Matching Accelup Experimentation Space
and Services with Innovators and Researchers

November 2025 | Version 3.0

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List of Abbreviations

WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
D	Deliverable
T	Task

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Executive Summary

The EVOLVE2CARE project aims to strengthen HealthTech innovation in transitional care by connecting Living Labs, innovators, and researchers across Europe and fostering harmonized experimentation. To support this mission, *the Training Program on Service Design for Living Labs*, which is described in this deliverable, was developed to equip Living Lab managers and coordinators, researchers, early-stage innovators, teams establishing new Living Labs, technology transfer professionals, and policymakers within the HealthTech sector with the practical skills, tools, and methodologies needed to strengthen their operations and enhance the services they provide to innovators from lab to market. The Training Programme was delivered online through six sessions between 24 June and 25 September 2025, and it was later added in the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy¹ on 25th October 2025 to allow those who could not attend the live sessions to access the content asynchronously.

D2.3 – Training Program for Living Labs highlights three key outcomes of the Training Programme. First, participants reported increased confidence in applying service design principles within their Living Labs, demonstrating that the training effectively built practical skills and actionable capacity. Second, the availability of recorded sessions and participation certificates through the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy extended the programme's reach, enabling asynchronous learning and providing formal recognition of engagement, which adds tangible value for participants. Third, the training emphasized the ongoing need for initiatives that bridge the gap between pilot creation and market deployment, underlining the importance of continued support for Living Labs to translate experimentation into sustainable impact.

In conclusion, this deliverable demonstrates how the Training Program enhanced Living Labs' capacity to translate innovations from pilot projects to market-ready solutions, directly supporting the EVOLVE2CARE project's long-term goals of fostering effective HealthTech innovation and sustainable impact.

¹ Access the course: <https://academy.enoll.org/course/trainingonservicesdesignforlivinglabs>

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project Overview

EVOLVE2CARE focuses on HealthTech experimentation practice to standardise and enhance the collaboration between Living Labs and innovators in the context of the Transitional Care sector. Challenges ranging from aging population to complexity of medical conditions and regulatory frameworks bring a growing recognition of the importance of experimentation practises. By subjecting innovations to real-world environments that involve end-users and stakeholders, EVOLVE2CARE provides innovators with access to services for testing and validating research and products.

The project focuses on three Use Cases (UC): i) Hospital discharge management; ii) Homecare monitoring solutions; and iii) Aging population & care transitions, engaging stakeholders across the whole value chain to examine complexities, barriers and enablers that regulatory framework poses to the development and commercialisation of healthcare innovations.

1.2 Work Package 2 and Task 2.3 Objectives

Work Package 2 (WP2) - Matching Accelup Experimentation Space and Services with Innovators and Researchers, coordinated by AUTH, has the main goal of creating an environment where real-world experimentation can be systematically supported, accelerated, and shared. To achieve this, WP2 includes several goals: the development of the Accelup experimentation space; the onboarding of Living Labs and innovators/researchers; and the design of tailored capacity-building programmes.

Within this context, Living Labs have the potential to act as key intermediaries, providing real-world testing environments and user-driven insights. However, not all Living Labs have the internal capacities or structured service models needed to support innovators effectively throughout the commercialisation pathway. Implemented by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), *Task 2.3 – Training Program for Living Labs* was therefore designed to strengthen these capacities by providing a dedicated and targeted training programme.

The programme aims to equip participants with a clear understanding of the wider innovation landscape, and the specific role Living Labs play within it, highlighting their contribution to societal and economic development. It introduces the practical methodologies needed for effective Living Lab operation, including user-engagement strategies, data collection techniques, project management practices, and quality

assurance approaches. Ethical considerations and compliance form a central part of the programme, ensuring that participants understand how to manage data responsibly, navigate privacy requirements, handle intellectual property, and operate within relevant legal frameworks.

Beyond technical competencies, the programme reinforces essential communication and collaboration skills to help Living Labs build stronger relationships with innovators, community members, and stakeholders. It also clarifies the process and benefits of becoming a Certified Living Lab, explains how to define and use meaningful metrics to assess impact, and prepares Living Labs to work effectively with startups and businesses through the Accelup platform. Finally, the programme supports engagement with regulators by helping participants understand how to present evidence from real-world testing in ways that facilitate regulatory adaptation when technology evolves faster than existing rules. Ultimately, this Capacity Building programme contributes to building a more sustainable innovation ecosystem grounded in collaboration between academia, industry, local communities, policymakers, and regulators.

These objectives are summarised in Figure 1, which provides an overview of the core elements addressed by the programme and how they collectively enhance the capacity of Living Labs to support innovators along the experimentation and commercialisation pathway.

Figure 1. Objectives of T2.3 - Training Program for Living Labs

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

Deliverable 2.3 (D2.3) – Training Program for Living Labs documents the design, implementation, and initial outcomes of the Training Program on Service Design for Living Labs, developed within Task 2.3 of the EVOLVE2CARE project and delivered by ENoLL. Its main purpose is to provide a comprehensive account of how the training was structured and delivered, illustrating the methodological approach, pedagogical design,

communication strategy, and supporting materials used to enhance the capacities of Living Labs.

Beyond serving as a record of activities, the deliverable offers insights for future Capacity Building efforts within the project, highlighting how structured training can enhance service design, operational maturity, and sustainable innovation practices within the Living Lab ecosystem.

1.4 Relation to T2.4 and D2.4

This deliverable is directly linked to *T2.4 – Training Program for Innovators and Researchers*, implemented by Anthology Ventures (AV). This training programme, led by AV, aims to provide researchers and innovators with the knowledge, skills, and strategies they need to effectively work with Living Labs and benefit from their services.

Because these two audiences interact closely in real innovation processes, both training programmes were designed to be complementary. During the preparation phase, ENoLL and AV collaborated to ensure that the content of the two trainings addressed distinct needs without overlapping, creating a coherent and well-aligned learning experience.

1.5 Structure

This deliverable (D2.3) is structured into eight sections that together provide a comprehensive overview of the task:

- **Section 1 Introduction:** Introduces the deliverable by outlining its purpose and structure, followed by a detailed explanation of the methodological approach used to design the training programme.
- **Section 2 Training Modules Overview:** Presents the training modules, describing their objectives, content, and structure within the overall learning pathway.
- **Section 3 Implementation and Delivery:** Describes how the training programme was implemented and delivered, detailing the formats, timelines, target groups, and operational arrangements.
- **Section 4 Evaluation and Feedback:** Summarises participants' feedback, highlighting key insights from the evaluation and demonstrating the programme's relevance, effectiveness, and usability.
- **Section 5 Lessons Learnt:** Reflects on the lessons learnt throughout the design and delivery process, identifying key takeaways and areas for future improvement.

- **Section 6 Dissemination and Sustainability:** Explains how the training and its outputs were disseminated and outlines how results can be sustained and leveraged over time.
- **Section 7 Impact of the Training Program:** Presents the impact generated by the training, illustrating how the activities contributed to capacity building and stakeholder engagement.
- **Section 8 Recommendations:** Provides recommendations for strengthening the development, replication, or expansion of the training programme.
- **Section 9 Conclusions and Next Steps:** Concludes the deliverable by summarising the main outcomes and outlining the next steps for sustaining and building upon the results.

2 Methodological Approach to Training Design

2.1 Topic Definition and Alignment with the Grant Agreement

The topic definition analysis was conducted in strict accordance with the specifications outlined in the Grant Agreement, which explicitly required a series of topics to be addressed with the training. These six topics were subsequently developed into six dedicated training modules, ensuring full alignment with the contractual requirements and the task objectives described in Section 1.2. Figure 2.

Figure 2. Task 2.3 Objectives and Corresponding Training Modules

2.2 Pedagogical Approach and Learning Design

The Training Programme was developed using a learner-centred pedagogical approach, ensuring that content, activities, and materials respond directly to the needs and realities of Living Labs operating within the healthcare and transitional care sectors. The design intentionally combines *solid theoretical foundations* with *structured opportunities for*

practical application, enabling participants not only to understand key concepts but also to translate them effectively into their operational environments.

To support this, each module was structured around a progressive learning pathway, beginning with conceptual grounding and moving towards increasingly applied and reflective exercises.

A variety of pedagogical techniques were intentionally blended to maximise engagement and knowledge retention:

- **Case-based learning:** Real-world examples and sector-specific scenarios allowed participants to critically examine challenges and decision-making processes typical of Living Lab operations.
- **Guided reflection:** Short reflective exercises supported participants in linking learning to their own contexts, fostering personal and organisational insight.
- **Experience-sharing dialogues:** Recognising that participants come from diverse Living Labs, structured peer exchange moments enabled them to learn from each other's practices, constraints, and successes.
- **Step-by-step demonstration of tools:** Templates, canvases, and methodological frameworks were explained through walkthroughs that modelled their use in real innovation processes.
- **Light-touch hands-on components:** Practical tools were included focused on individual application.

The programme also followed principles of accessibility, inclusiveness, and adaptability. Content was designed to be relevant for Living Labs at different maturity levels from newly established, evolving, to highly experienced, by ensuring that explanations remained rigorous yet approachable. Participants were supported with:

- **Comprehensive presentations** summarising key concepts in clear, structured formats.
- **Practical templates and checklists** enabling immediate application after the training.
- **Step-by-step guides** for methodologies discussed in the modules.
- **Additional reading and reference materials** for those wishing to deepen their knowledge further.

Finally, the learning design ensured long-term usability by keeping all training materials continuously accessible through the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy. By hosting the recorded sessions, tools, and supporting resources on the platform, learners can revisit the content at any time, apply the methodologies at their own pace, and integrate the materials into their internal processes. This ongoing access enables participants to

consolidate skills beyond the live sessions and supports the sustained strengthening of Living Lab practices in alignment with the objectives of the EVOLVE2CARE and Accelup frameworks

3 Training Program Overview

This section provides an overview of the Training Programme, outlining its objectives, structure, and pedagogical approach, as well as the thematic focus of each module delivered to support Living Labs operating in the health and wellbeing domain.

3.1 Structure of the Training Curriculum

The *Training on Service Design for Living Labs* was structured as a six-module Capacity Building programme. While each module addressed a distinct aspect of Living Lab activity, the entire curriculum was anchored in a service design approach, ensuring that participants understood how to build user-centred, evidence-based, and operationally coherent services that can effectively support innovators at different stages of the innovation pathway.

The structure followed a clear learning progression. It began by situating Living Labs within the wider innovation ecosystem and then moved into the core of the programme: how to design tailored services that translate real-world experimentation into added value for innovators and researchers. Subsequent modules explored the enabling conditions required for these services to function, regulatory compliance, stakeholder engagement, standardisation, and impact measurement. In this way, the curriculum reflected the full lifecycle of a Living Lab service, from conception to evaluation.

The six training modules included in the programme, illustrated in Figure 3 and detailed in Section 3.2 were:

1. **The Role of Living Labs in the Innovation Ecosystem:** Setting the foundation by clarifying where Living Labs sit in the innovation landscape and why structured service design is essential for generating societal and economic value.
2. **Designing Tailored Living Lab Services for Innovators:** Introducing the principles and steps of service design, emphasising user-centred methodologies and practical tools to structure services that respond effectively to innovators' needs.
3. **Navigating Legal, Ethical & Regulatory Frameworks:** Exploring how compliance, ethics, data protection, and intellectual property considerations must be integrated into the design and delivery of Living Lab services from the outset.
4. **Building Innovation Networks: Communication and Engagement:** Focusing on designing engagement pathways that enable effective collaboration with innovators, businesses, communities, academia, and regulators.

5. **Certification & Standardisation of Living Labs:** Presenting the standardised certification process followed by ENOLL for the labelling and certification of Living Labs.
6. **Measuring Impact & Evaluating Success:** Introducing Key Impact Indicators (KIIs) and evaluation frameworks that allow Living Labs to assess service performance and demonstrate value in real-world deployment.

Figure 3. Modules of the Training program for Living Labs

Overall, the curriculum provided a structured and comprehensive pathway for Living Labs to strengthen their service design capacities and optimise their role in supporting innovation across the health and wellbeing sector.

3.2 Detailed Description of Training Modules

This section provides a concise overview of the content, objectives, and key themes addressed in each of the six training modules delivered under *Task 2.3 – Training Program for Living Labs*.

3.2.1 Module 1: The Role of Living Labs in the Innovation Ecosystem

Date: 25 June 2025 | Participants: 28

This introductory module addressed the foundational concepts of Living Labs, outlining their origins, core principles, and positioning within the broader innovation landscape. Presentations highlighted the value of user-driven innovation, collaborative experimentation, and real-life testing environments - particularly in sectors such as

healthcare and transitional care. Participants were introduced to practical examples demonstrating how Living Labs generate value for innovators and society.

Table 1. Agenda Session 1

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
The Innovation Ecosystem	Dimitri Schuurman – ENoLL, uGhent, imec
How LiCaLab support innovators	Ingrid Adriaensen - LiCalab
How CRIC supports innovators	Eva Kehayia - CRIR
How SuaraLab supports innovators	Clara G. Garcia Blanch - Suara
How Intras supports innovators	Raquel Losada - Intras
Q&A	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

The session opened with Prof. Schuurman, who framed Living Labs within the broader innovation landscape, tracing their evolution from the Triple Helix model to the Quadruple Helix, which integrates civil society alongside government, academia, and industry.

He highlighted the strategic value of Living Labs in open innovation, emphasising their role in value creation, co-creation, and real-life experimentation. He also introduced a framework for navigating complexity across strategic, tactical, and operational levels and stressed the importance of anchoring Living Labs in a clear mission and vision, supported by ecosystem-driven approaches. Practical implementation was described across three layers: organizational multi-actor orchestration, project-level experimentation, and activity-level stakeholder engagement.

The session then presented case studies from four Living Labs, showcasing diverse approaches to user-centred innovation.

Ingrid Adriaensen presented LiCalab² based in Belgium, which supports care technology development through a large citizen and professional panel and collaborations with hospitals and municipalities, emphasizing inclusivity and sustainability.

² Read more: <https://enoll.org/member/licalab-living-and-care-lab/>

Dr. Eva Kehayia described RehabMaLL³ in Canada, a rehabilitation Living Lab embedded in a public mall, combining real-world and simulated environments for co-designing assistive technologies.

Clara García Blanch from Social Digital Lab Suara⁴ in Spain highlighted a person-centred, co-creative Living Lab using immersive and virtual reality to promote digital inclusion, cognitive stimulation, and well-being.

Sofía Ballesteros Rodríguez presented MINDLab⁵ in Spain, focusing on mental health and cognitive impairments, supporting co-design, digital health solutions, assistive technologies, and independent living initiatives, with VIVEMAIS illustrating cross-border collaboration in assistive technology development.

3.2.2 Module 2: Designing Tailored Living Lab Services for Innovators

Date: 9 July 2025 | Participants: 20

This module focused on service design methodologies, providing participants with tools and frameworks to develop tailored Living Lab services. Through case examples and practical guidance, the module illustrated how Living Labs can co-create solutions with innovators, prototype service concepts, and plan user engagement activities aligned with innovation goals and stakeholder needs.

Table 2 Agenda Session 2

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
What is Service Design?	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
Case Study: Thessaloniki Action for Health & Wellbeing Living Lab	Despoina Petsani - AUTH
The language and goals of Service Design	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
The Service Design Process	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
Basics of Pricing Living Lab Services	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
Q&A	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

³ Read more: <https://enoll.org/member/rehabilitation-living-lab-in-the-mall/>

⁴ Read more: <https://enoll.org/member/social-digital-lab-suara/>

⁵ Read more: <https://enoll.org/member/mindlab/>

Francesca Sperandio introduced the fundamentals of Service Design, highlighting its human-centred, evidence-based, and iterative approach, which mirrors Living Labs' emphasis on co-creation and real-life experimentation.

Despoina Petsani presented case studies from the Thessaloniki Action for Health & Wellbeing Living Lab⁶ in Greece, highlighting pilot projects such as ASSURE (an AI tool for dysphagia detection) and HESTIA (a thermal monitoring system for informal caregiving). She illustrated the significant coordination, time, and personnel required for internal teams versus external visiting researchers, underscoring the resource-intensive nature of effective Living Lab services.

Marta I. De Los Ríos White presented a structured five-step process: Discover, Define, Develop, Deliver, and Evolve, for turning Living Lab activities into repeatable, well-defined services. She also offered guidance on pricing strategies, emphasizing the importance of assessing the value provided to innovators, calculating internal costs, and ensuring alignment with the Lab's mission and financial sustainability.

To support this work in practice, the Living Lab Service Blueprint template was introduced as a tool to map key touchpoints, actors, and processes, helping Living Labs plan and visualize services in a human-centred, repeatable, and sustainable way.

⁶ Read more: <https://enoll.org/member/thessaloniki-action-for-health-wellbeing-living-lab/>

Figure 4 Living Lab Service Blueprint template

3.2.3 Module 3: Navigating Legal, Ethical & Regulatory Frameworks

Date: 23 July 2025 | Participants: 21

This training addressed the legal and ethical considerations that Living Labs need to incorporate into their work. Experts covered data protection and privacy requirements, informed consent, intellectual property rights, and regulatory obligations. Specific attention was given to the challenges that arise when dealing with sensitive data, digital health solutions, and multi-stakeholder research environments.

Table 3 Agenda Session 3

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Key Legal Considerations for LLs	Maria Iakovidou - Lawyer
How to address legal and ethical issues: examples from practice	Abdolrasoul Habibipour - Botnia Living Lab
Tool Time: Starter Checklist for LLs	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

Maria Iakovidou, Lawyer at Supreme Court in Greece, opened the session by emphasizing that Living Labs, by their very nature involving different stakeholders in their work. There is also an urgent need making compliance with legal frameworks essential for protecting participants, ensuring transparency, and avoiding any type of conflict that may arise. She equipped the participants with the legal basics to be compliant: a detailed overview of GDPR requirements, the importance of properly documenting informed consent, intellectual property management, and risk and liability considerations.

Dr. Abdolrasoul Habibipour representing Botnia Living Lab in Sweden, presented a structured approach to integrating ethical and legal considerations into Living Lab design. He explored key principles such as stakeholder engagement, transparency, and real-life experimentation. He illustrated their application through case studies from EU projects like SynAir-G and U4IoT, highlighting practical strategies for managing consent, data protection, IP rights, and liability.

As a final recommendation, Dr. Abdolrasoul Habibipour encouraged participants to adopt a structured approach to ethics by creating internal checklists for each phase of a Living Lab project (design, pilot, exploitation, and dissemination). These checklists should cover consent, risk, inclusion, and data handling, and include “red flag” prompts such as: *Would I be comfortable if this were done to me? Could this unintentionally harm or exclude anyone? Would this pass a newspaper test?* By pausing and consulting ethics or legal support whenever something feels questionable, teams can embed ethical reflection into their daily routines. To support this process, participants were equipped with a practical ethical checklist, designed to guide them throughout their innovation journey.

3.2.4 Module 4: Building Innovation Networks: Communication and Engagement

Date: 3 September 2025 | Participants: 16

The fourth module explored strategies for effective communication, community building, and stakeholder engagement. Participants learned how to position their Living Lab as a credible and collaborative partner, how to manage relationships with diverse stakeholder groups -including public authorities, academia, SMEs, startups, and user communities- and how to leverage communication channels to strengthen their visibility and network.

Table 4 Agenda Session 4

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

Stakeholder Engagement Example from Social Digital Lab (Suara)	Clara Garcia Blanch - Suara
Stakeholder Engagement Example from LiCalab	Leen Broeckx - LiCalab
Stakeholder Engagement	Marta I. De Los Ríos White - ENoLL
Stakeholder Engagement in Living Labs	Despoina Petsani - AUTH
Q&A	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

The session opened with practical insights shared by Clara Garcia Blanch from Social Digital Lab (Suara) and Leen Broeckx from LiCalab, offering concrete examples of stakeholder engagement within Living Lab environments.

 Clara Garcia Blanch reflected on the complexity of identifying and involving stakeholders in co-creation processes. She emphasised that effective innovation goes beyond engaging the most visible actors , often, less apparent stakeholders can have a significant impact on project outcomes. For this reason, **active listening** is essential to truly understand and address their perspectives. Without it, the main challenges of stakeholder engagement cannot be overcome, namely:

- Time: meaningful engagement requires time, which is often limited during project implementation.
- Network and ecosystem: collaboration with local organisations and community networks is crucial to ensure relevance and long-term impact.
- Professional roles: professionals working within communities need to be present and increase the frequency of interactions, while also developing new skills to manage relationships effectively.
- Person-centred approach: citizens should not be treated as passive recipients but as active contributors in designing solutions that shape their daily lives.

 Leen Broeckx presented how LiCalab systematically manages stakeholder participation in health and care innovation. The Living Lab operates within real-life testing environments that bring together citizens and care professionals. Leen explained how stakeholders are classified as internal or external and how analytical tools, such as power-interest grids, help determine engagement strategies.

Subsequently, the discussion shifted from practice to theory, with Marta I. De Los Ríos White providing a conceptual framework for stakeholder engagement. She clarified the distinctions between stakeholders, users, and customers, and introduced key classification models (internal/external, primary/secondary, direct/indirect). In the context of Living Labs, stakeholders are typically represented through the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM), which identifies four main groups - the public sector, businesses, academia, and civil society - as the core pillars of collaborative innovation.

Figure 5. Stakeholder Categories Following the Quadruple Helix Model

Finally, Despoina Petsani built on the theory with one last

comprehensive example of how the *Thessaloniki Active and Healthy Ageing Living Lab (Thess-AHALL)* showcased how structured engagement and long-term collaboration can transform a Living Lab into a robust innovation ecosystem. Despoina Petsani introduced several digital tools including *Accelup* that facilitates ongoing interaction between innovators and citizens. Thess-AHALL's experience demonstrated how trust-building, continuity, and well-designed tools help Living Labs evolve into sustainable and impactful innovation environments.

3.2.5 Module 5: Certification & Standardisation of Living Labs

Date: 10 September 2025 | Participants: 15

This module provided an overview of the ENoLL Living Lab certification process, including the criteria, benefits, and procedural steps involved. It explained how alignment with recognised standards contributes to enhanced quality, credibility, and sustainability of Living Lab operations. Participants were exposed to best practices from internationally certified Living Labs, offering a practical understanding of the certification journey.

Table 5 Agenda Session 5

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio -ENoLL

Overview of Certification	Gabriella Quaranta - ENoLL
Key Requirements for Certification & Evaluation Criteria	Alessandra Tricarico - ENoLL
Application Material and steps	Alessandra Tricarico - ENoLL
Benefits of Certification	Gabriella Quaranta - ENoLL
Q&A	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

A key focus of the session, highlighted by Gabriella Quaranta and Alessandra Tricarico, was the concept of **harmonisation**, which ensures that all assessments are conducted consistently and transparently across applicants. This approach not only strengthens the credibility and comparability of Living Labs worldwide but also provides guidance for continuous improvement, linking strategic objectives with operational practices and supporting the long-term development and sustainability of innovation ecosystems.

This framework is organized into six core chapters, strategy, users & reality, operations, openness, value & impact, and stability & scale-up, encompassing 15 evaluation criteria. These chapters collectively assess the organizational, methodological, and operational dimensions of a Living Lab, ensuring that diversity in type, scope, and regional context is fully considered.

A harmonised evaluation framework

The harmonized Living Lab evaluation framework developed by ENoLL consists of 15 evaluation criteria clustered into 6 Evaluation Chapters.

1. Strategy

- Governance
- Business Model
- Culture & collaboration

2. Operations

- Human resources
- Operations
- Equipment & infrastructure

3. Openness

- Innovation partnerships, projects & processes
- Ownership of results

4. Users & Reality

- User-centricity
- Lifecycle & real-life
- Tools & methods

5. Impact & Value

- Co-created values
- Impacts

6. Stability & Harmonization

- Stability
- Harmonization & scale-up

Vervoort et al, 2022
<https://zenodo.org/records/7434406>

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Figure 6. The Harmonized Living Lab Evaluation Framework

The certification is operationalized through two complementary tools:

1. The Self-Assessment Tool⁷, providing a quantitative overview of a Living Lab’s performance and generating a personalised evaluation report.
2. The Qualitative Application Form, allowing a description of organisational structure, governance, partnerships, and innovation practices.

By combining these quantitative and qualitative lenses, the process ensures **comprehensive, balanced, and fair evaluation**, while also providing practical feedback to strengthen innovation capacity.

Ultimately, the module puts emphasis on how **certification connects theory to practice** was a key topic discussed, as it links the strategic mission and vision of a Living Lab with concrete operational measures, aligns diverse stakeholders under harmonized standards, and creates a foundation for continuous learning and innovation. In this way, ENoLL certification becomes both a **quality assurance mechanism** and a **strategic tool** for Living Labs striving to scale, improve, and generate sustainable value for their ecosystems.

3.2.6 Module 6: Measuring Impact & Evaluating Success

Date: 24 September 2025 | Participants: 16

The final module focused on impact assessment frameworks and performance evaluation methods. Participants explored metrics and indicators for measuring innovation outcomes, user engagement, service performance, and societal impact. Emphasis was placed on evidence-based evaluation to demonstrate value creation, support decision-making, and sustain long-term Living Lab operations.

Table 6 Agenda Session 6

Item	Speaker/Moderator
Welcome & Intro	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Measuring Impact & Evaluating Success	Dimitri Schuurman – ENoLL, uGhent, imec
Q&A	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL
Wrap-Up	Francesca Sperandio - ENoLL

⁷ <https://survey.sogolytics.com/survey/form?k=RRsRVVPWWsQWsPsPsP&lang=0>

The session began by examining the core characteristics of Living Labs⁸, including multi-stakeholder collaboration, continuous user involvement, co-creation, orchestration of activities, real-world testing environments, and flexible methodological approaches. Understanding these features is essential for designing effective evaluation strategies.

Dimitri Schuurman introduced participants to evaluation frameworks, including the Impact Model and the Living Lab Assessment Method⁹, designed to help Living Labs monitor progress and assess outcomes. He emphasized the importance of distinguishing between outputs -what was done - and outcomes - the actual change or benefits achieved. To ensure meaningful impact, pilots should begin with clearly defined objectives and measurable goals, closely aligned with the needs of users and other stakeholders.

⁸ European Network of Living Labs, Schuurman, D., DeLosRíos-White, M. I., & Desole, M. (2025). Living Lab origins, developments, and future perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14764597>

⁹ Robaeyst, B., & Baccarne, B. (2024). Living Lab Assessment Method (LLAM) : towards a methodology for context-sensitive value assessments. XXXV ISPIIM Innovation Conference, Proceedings. Presented at the XXXV ISPIIM Innovation Conference, Tallinn, Estonia.

Impact model

Figure 7. Impact Model

Participants were encouraged to define 2–3 priority outcomes for each pilot, aligned with user and stakeholder needs, and to apply SMART indicators: Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound to track progress effectively.

Dimitri Schuurman highlighted scaling pilots responsibly as a key stage, emphasizing that growth should be evidence-driven and context-sensitive. Three paths to scale were presented: replication (applying the same model in similar settings), adaptation (tailoring solutions to new contexts while preserving core principles), and dissemination (sharing knowledge, tools, and frameworks for independent replication). Success relies on strong user feedback, operational readiness, and alignment with technology, business models, policies, and broader systems.

The session concluded with a central message: embedding evaluation from the outset is critical not only for reporting purposes but also as a driver for learning, growth, and evidence-based scaling of innovations.

4 Implementation and Delivery

This section outlines how the Training Programme on Service Design for Living Labs was delivered, detailing the planning, scheduling, participation, and supporting resources that underpinned its successful implementation. It highlights the structure and format of the six online modules, the strategies employed to ensure accessibility and engagement across a diverse audience, and the practical tools provided to participants

4.1 Communication and Call for Participation

To engage Living Labs effectively and ensure broad participation, a targeted communication strategy accompanied an open call for the Training Program. The call, carefully designed by ENoLL, aimed to reach as many relevant stakeholders as possible across the network. The campaign leveraged all ENoLL channels, social media, newsletters. Additionally, all members of the Health & Wellbeing Working Group - comprising over 130 participants from both Living Labs and external organisations - were personally invited to join the training.

ViLabs further reinforced visibility and engagement by implementing a comprehensive communication plan for the training activities. Announcements were shared on EVOLVE2CARE's social media channels and complemented by dedicated event pages with automated reminders for registered participants.

After each online session, ViLabs developed recap articles highlighting the key points of each session were published on the project website and promoted via social media, extending the sessions' impact beyond the live attendees.

4.2 Training Delivery

The Training Programme on Service Design for Living Labs was delivered through a series of six online sessions held between 25 June 2025 and 24 September 2025. Each session lasted between 60 and 90 minutes and was consistently scheduled from 15:00 to 16:00 CET.

After completing the Training Programme, all recorded sessions were uploaded in the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy¹⁰, where they will remain publicly accessible beyond the end of the project in October 2026, allowing participants to attend the sessions

¹⁰ Find the training here: <https://academy.enoll.org/course/trainingservicesdesignforlivinglabs>

asynchronously. The platform’s user-friendly design ensures easy navigation, with each session presented alongside descriptions, supporting materials, and recordings, facilitating a comprehensive learning experience.

Up to the submission of this deliverable, a total of 116 unique participants attended the training live, , which can be shown in Figure 8 below, while 37 participants are currently following it asynchronously on the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy. Among these, 10 representatives from ENoLL certified Living Labs attended the live sessions, while 2 additional certified Living Labs are participating asynchronously via the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy. This reflects a diverse audience of professionals and practitioners engaged in health, wellbeing, and innovation activities, moving closer to the KPI target set in the project of 20 Living Labs participating in the training. Certificates of participation were awarded to all participants who completed at least four of the six sessions. To date, 10 participants have met this requirement through live attendance, and an additional 5 have completed the programme asynchronously, all of whom received their certificates. The breakdown of participants that took part during the live sessions is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Training Participation Breakdown

4.3 Training Materials and Resources

The Training Programme combined theoretical frameworks with practical insights, providing participants with tools to design, implement, and evaluate Living Lab services efficiently. Each session was accompanied by comprehensive supporting materials, including PowerPoint presentations, which summarize the key concepts, case studies, and methodologies discussed.

Participants also received practical resources to support their ongoing activities:

- **Living Lab Service Blueprint template:** A tool to map key touchpoints, actors, and processes, enabling Living Labs to plan and visualize services in a human-centred, repeatable, and sustainable way.
- **Ethics Checklist:** A practical guide to integrate ethical considerations into all phases of Living Lab activities, ensuring responsible and inclusive practices.

The materials have been made available to learners in the online course.

5 Evaluation Feedback

At the end of the Training Program for Living Labs, an evaluation feedback form was shared to assess the overall quality, relevance, and impact on participants. The feedback process aimed to determine how effectively the training met its learning objectives, supported Living Labs in strengthening their operational and service design capacities, and provided actionable knowledge for practical implementation.

5.1 Evaluation Approach

The post-session feedback form for the Training on Service Design for Living Labs was designed to capture both quantitative and qualitative insights from participants. It aimed to assess the overall quality of the training, its relevance to participants' professional needs, and the practical applicability of the knowledge and tools provided. To achieve this, the survey combined 5-point Likert scale questions with open-ended items, allowing participants to provide more detailed feedback and suggestions.

On one hand, participants were asked to rate aspects such as the overall quality of each session, the relevance of the content to their needs as a Living Lab, the knowledge and clarity of the speakers, the applicability of actionable tools and frameworks, the opportunities for interaction and Q&A, the pacing and structure of the sessions, and the usefulness of the provided materials. They were also asked whether the content matched their current stage of Living Lab development, whether their understanding of key topics (such as Service Design and the role of Living Labs in the innovation landscape) improved, and whether they felt confident applying what they learned.

On the other hand, Open-ended questions invited participants to suggest additional topics or areas for deeper exploration, and to self-assess their readiness to engage in the commercialisation of Living Lab services, ranging from being unsure to actively offering services or collaborating with innovators.

The feedback form was developed by Vilabs and disseminated right after the completion of the training through the project's social networks and the participants' mailing list. To ensure wider access, it was also added to the course on the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy at the end of the six module. Responses will continue to be collected until the end of the project, ensuring that all participants have the opportunity to contribute their feedback.

5.2 Participants’ Feedback

The evaluation feedback has been so far submitted by 7 participants: 4 who attended the live sessions, and 3 who completed the course online. However, this number is expected to increase in the coming months as more participants engage with the training through the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy.

The first question assessed the overall quality of each session, with all modules receiving ratings between 3 and 5 on a 5-point scale, indicating a consistently positive participant experience (Table 7. Q1 Overall quality per session). Modules such as *“The Role of Living Labs in the Innovation Ecosystem,”* *“Designing Tailored Living Lab Services for Innovators,”* and *“Certification & Standardization of Living Labs”* received particularly strong ratings, with most participants assigning them the highest scores. By contrast, *“Navigating Legal, Ethical & Regulatory Frameworks”* and *“Building Innovation Networks: Communication and Engagement”* showed a slightly wider spread of ratings (3 to 5), reflecting diverse perceptions of relevance depending on participants’ backgrounds. A small number of N/A responses correspond to participants who could not attend specific sessions. Overall, the results confirm that the training was well-received, with especially high interest in practical and strategic topics that directly support Living Lab operations and impact.

Table 7. Q1 Overall quality per session

For the more detailed questions concerning the content and delivery of the training (Q2–Q11), the feedback shows a consistently positive experience. Participants generally agreed that the sessions were relevant to their needs as Living Labs (Table 8. Q2. The sessions I attended were relevant to my needs as a Living Lab and they found the speakers knowledgeable and clear in their explanations (Table 9. Q3. The speaker(s) were knowledgeable and communicated clearly. Many reported that they gained practical tools and frameworks they could put into use right away (Table 10. Q4. I gained

actionable tools or frameworks I can apply immediately and they appreciated having enough time for questions and interaction during the sessions (Table 11. Q5. There was sufficient time and opportunity for Q&A and interaction

The structure and pacing of the programme were also well received, helping participants follow the material smoothly (Table 12. Q.6 The pacing and structure supported my learning. Training resources, such as slides and handouts, were considered clear, useful, and well organised (Table 13. Q7. Slides/handouts/resources were clear, useful, and well-organized). Respondents felt that the content matched their current stage of Living Lab development (Table 14) whether they were just starting or already operating more mature structures, and that their understanding improved on key topics addressed during the programme (Table 15)

Table 8. Q2. The sessions I attended were relevant to my needs as a Living Lab

Table 9. Q3. The speaker(s) were knowledgeable and communicated clearly

Table 10. Q4. I gained actionable tools or frameworks I can apply immediately

Table 11. Q5. There was sufficient time and opportunity for Q&A and interaction

Table 12. Q.6 The pacing and structure supported my learning

Table 13. Q7. Slides/handouts/resources were clear, useful, and well-organized

Table 14. Q8. The content matched my current stage (from Living Lab idea to Living Lab scale up)

Table 15. Q9. My understanding improved on key topics (Service Design for Living Labs and their role in the Innovation Landscape)

For what concerns what participants feel they can take away from the training, they reported a strong sense of confidence in applying what they learned in the short term

(Table 16) with most indicating that they feel ready to use the tools and insights gained during the sessions within the next 30 days. They also agreed that the series addressed the right topics with an appropriate level of depth for their needs (Table 17).

When asked to reflect on their post-training status (Table 18) responses showed that 42.9% of participants are already committed and actively taking action - offering services or collaborating with innovators - while 28.6% indicated they are preparing to offer services within the next three to six months. Another 28.6% expressed that they are unsure and need additional information or support. These results not only demonstrate the immediate impact of the training in empowering Living Labs to act on what they have learned but also highlight the ongoing need for similar initiatives. The proportion of participants still seeking guidance underscores the value of continuing capacity-building efforts to bridge the gap between experimentation and market-ready implementation.

Table 16. Q10. I feel confident applying what I learned in the next 30 days

Table 17. Q11. The series covered the right topics and depth for my needs

Table 18. Q12. Participants' Readiness to Engage in Living Lab Service Commercialisation

Q12. After these sessions, which best describes you?

6 Lessons Learnt

Delivering the Training Programme provided valuable insights into what makes capacity-building for Living Labs most effective. One key lesson was the importance of combining conceptual understanding with concrete, practice-oriented content. Participants responded particularly well during the Q&A to sessions where methods and tools were demonstrated through real examples and discussion.

Another important lesson concerned the comprehensive structure of the six-session series, which successfully addressed the diverse needs of Living Labs at different maturity levels, from emerging initiatives still defining their identity and services to well-established Living Labs looking to refine or scale their operations. This layered approach ensured that all participants, regardless of their level of experience, were able to draw practical insights and apply them within their specific contexts.

Feedback from the participants highlighted the importance of expanding the training to cover business models and sustainability strategies for Living Labs. Additionally, the need for practical engagement tools that account for stakeholders' levels of involvement at each phase of the innovation process was emphasized. These insights suggest that future training initiatives should not only focus on service design and operational methodologies but also provide a more in-depth guidance on sustainable business practices and stakeholder management to maximize the impact of Living Labs

Finally, the training program reaffirmed the strategic importance of service design training as a cornerstone for Living Lab sustainability. Strengthening competences in this area is crucial for the long self-sustainability of Living Labs.

7 Dissemination and Sustainability

The Training Program on Service Design for Living Labs was designed to equip participants with practical skills, tools, and strategic perspectives to enhance the effectiveness and sustainability of their Living Labs. Covering the full spectrum of Living Lab operations.

7.1 Public Availability via the ENoLL Living Labbers Platform

Figure 9. Training Card on the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy

Following the completion of the Training Program, all session materials and recordings were uploaded to the [ENoLL Living Labbers Academy](#) and have been publicly available since 25 October 2025.

The decision to host the trainings on this platform was made to ensure that

they remain valuable and accessible for all participants, including those following the course asynchronously.

The platform itself is very user-friendly and easy to navigate. In the Training section of the platform, participants can access an overview of each session through a dedicated box containing a brief description of the content. This allows users to quickly understand the focus and objectives of each module. Once enrolled in the course, participants can watch the full session recordings and consult all supporting materials, enabling a deeper engagement with the training content at their own pace.

Currently, 37 new participants have enrolled in the course and are actively following the sessions and 5 have obtained the certificate of participation after completing all modules through the platform.

This open-access approach also lays the foundation for the long-term impact and future use of the program, as Living Labs can revisit the materials, apply the methods in their own contexts, and continue building their capacities over time.

7.2 Long-Term Impact and Future Use

The Training Program on Service Design for Living Labs has offered participants more than immediate guidance or practical tools - it has fostered a mindset of reflection and strategic thinking that can influence both their organisations and the wider innovation ecosystem over time. Through the six modules, participants have been exposed to the full spectrum of Living Lab operations, from understanding their place within the innovation landscape to designing services, engaging stakeholders, navigating ethical and regulatory frameworks, and measuring impact effectively. These experiences encourage participants to consider how their Living Lab can evolve, respond to real-world challenges, and deliver tangible value to innovators and communities alike.

Making all materials, including recordings and resources, available on the ENOLL Living Labbers Academy ensures that the programme's impact can extend beyond the participants who attended live sessions.

Beyond immediate operational improvements, the programme has fostered a mindset oriented toward sustainability, collaboration, and evidence-based decision-making. Participants are encouraged to integrate these approaches into their daily workflows, influencing how they design services, engage stakeholders, and evaluate outcomes.

8 Conclusions and Next Steps

The EVOLVE2CARE Training Programme on Service Design for Living Labs offered a structured, comprehensive learning journey tailored to the health and wellbeing sector. Spanning six modules, the programme guided participants through the full innovation pathway, from understanding the strategic role of Living Labs and designing tailored services to navigating legal and ethical frameworks, engaging stakeholders, and measuring impact to support the scaling of pilot initiatives.

Several key lessons emerged from the programme. Blending theoretical content with practical tools, such as the Living Lab Service Blueprint and Ethics Checklist, proved essential to helping participants visualize processes and structure their activities. The modules successfully addressed the needs of a diverse audience, including newly established Living Labs with limited prior experience and more mature Living Labs aiming to refine or expand their services.

The training also yielded tangible engagement outcomes. Based on the participants' self-assessment at the end of the programme (Table 18), 42% reported that they are already committed and actively taking action, either by offering services or by collaborating with innovators. A further 28% indicated that they are ready to offer services to innovators within the next 3–6 months, demonstrating a strong forward-looking engagement. These results reflect both the relevance of the content and the readiness of participants to translate learning into practice. Conversely, 28.8% stated that they remain unsure and would require additional information or support before moving forward. This highlights the importance of continuing to strengthen capacity-building initiatives of this kind,

Looking ahead, the materials and recordings remain accessible on the ENoLL Living Labbers Academy. Planned follow-up activities include monitoring how many new participants engage until the end of the project and understand if Living Labs apply the methodologies and tools gathered during the full training.

In conclusion, the Training Programme successfully delivered essential theoretical knowledge while equipping Living Labs with actionable tools and resources. These resources are designed to support daily operations, enable evidence-based decision-making, and foster long-term strategic growth across the health and wellbeing innovation ecosystem.

9 Annexes

Annex A – Ethics Checklist

Living Lab Legal & Ethical Starter Checklist

Use this checklist during service design, before pilots, and when co-creating services in Living Labs. It supports legal compliance, ethical awareness, and trust-building with users and partners. Adapt it to your project needs.

1. Data Protection (GDPR)

- Have we clearly defined what personal data we're collecting?
- Do we have a legal basis for processing it (e.g., consent)?
- Is data minimized – only what's truly necessary?
- Are there data retention and deletion plans in place?
- Is a DPIA (Data Protection Impact Assessment) needed?

2. Informed Consent

- Do users understand what they're participating in?
- Can users say no without pressure?
- Is consent documented (digital, verbal, signed)?
- Is it possible to withdraw consent easily later?
- Are special groups (children, elderly) given tailored information?

3. Intellectual Property (IP)

- Have we agreed who owns the innovation or data created?
- Is the output open-source, proprietary, or shared?
- Do partners/users know how results can be reused?
- Have we documented agreements (e.g., MoU, NDA, CC license)?
- Are we using or combining third-party IP (e.g., code, content)?

4. Risk and Liability

- Could anyone be harmed physically or emotionally in this pilot?
- Have we discussed insurance or waivers if needed?
- Are we testing unfinished or experimental tech?
- Is an ethics review needed before launch?
- Have we prepared a risk mitigation plan?

5. Inclusion & Vulnerable Users

- Are we involving diverse participants (age, gender, culture)?
- Are vulnerable groups (e.g., children, elderly, migrants) protected?
- Is participation voluntary and free from pressure?

- Are accessibility needs considered (e.g., visual, cognitive)?
- Are language barriers or literacy levels addressed?

6. Transparency & Communication

- Do users know why the LL is collecting data and what will happen with it?
- Are there clear contact persons for questions or complaints?
- Are we using plain language (no legal jargon)?
- Is there a simple privacy notice or info sheet?
- Are decisions explained back to users after pilots?

7. Ethics Embedded in Design

- Are ethical discussions part of project planning?
- Is there space for user feedback on ethical concerns?
- Do we reflect on unintended consequences?
- Are we guided by values like autonomy, fairness, sustainability?
- Are ethics reviewed at key milestones?